

Studies on the complexation behaviour of copper(II) ions with polyamidoamine (PAMAM) dendron

Samaresh Ghosh

Department of Chemistry, Bankura Sammilani College, Bankura-722 102, West Bengal, India

E-mail : gsamaresh@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Spectral and electrochemical studies have been carried out for the investigation of the complexation behaviour of polytopic dendritic ligand (PAMAM) towards Cu^{II} ion. Formation of the complex was clear from the UV-Vis *d-d* transition band. Cyclic voltammetric study of the dendron- Cu^{II} complex revealed chemically irreversible behaviour.

Keywords : Copper(II), complexation behaviour, dendron.

Dendrimers possessing unique structures and properties have received considerable research interest in recent years^{1,2}. Their branched, compartmentalized structures are attractive nanoscopic building blocks for the design and synthesis of a variety of novel functional materials. However, polyamidoamine (PAMAM) dendrimers^{3,4} constitute important part of the novel class of dendritic macromolecules because of their novel structural properties and attractive potential applications in various fields.

In this context, the interesting development of PAMAM dendrimer chemistry concerns the coordination of metal ions by the interior/exterior units^{5,6}. However, the motive investigation of coordinative interaction between metal ions and PAMAM dendrimers is due to the following reasons : (i) presence of great number of amine, ester and amide groups that can easily coordinate with the metal ions, (ii) coordination of metal ions in the interior branches will generate novel nanocomposites for various potential applications, (iii) due to structural resemblance of PAMAM dendrimers with biomolecules like proteins and enzymes, mechanism of complex formation may have strong biological relevance.

Therefore, continuing our investigation in the field of PAMAM dendrimers⁷, this paper reports the coordination properties of our previously developed polytopic PAMAM dendritic diol ligands with copper(II) ions. Particular interest with this PAMAM dendritic diol is due to its use as an important precursor for the development of various novel PAMAM side chain dendritic polymers (SCDPs)⁷. Moreover, Cu^{II} ion has been chosen for the complexation study because of its well-defined and well-

extensive chemistry⁸.

Results and discussion

We have recently reported⁷ the synthesis of ester terminated PAMAM dendritic diol **1** via Michael addition and amidation processes. Complexation of this prototypic dendritic ligand with Cu^{II} ion was investigated by UV-Vis spectroscopy. Upon addition of methanolic solution of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to the methanolic solution of **1**, the yellowish colour of the dendrimer solution gradually turned to deep blue and finally became bluish green with further addition of Cu^{II} ions.

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PAMAM dendritic diol

Formation of this complex with blue and bluish green colorations associated with a broad absorption band at 650 nm belonging to the copper *d-d* transition was observed in the UV-Vis spectrum (Fig. 1). During titration, the intensity of *d-d* transition band gradually increases on successive addition of Cu^{II} ions and reaches a maximum demonstrating its strong complexation. The number of copper(II) ions complexed into each dendrimer has been quantitatively assessed by spectrophotometric titration. A summary of the titration results (Fig. 2) indicates that the absorbance at λ_{max} 650 nm increases with the ratio of [Cu²⁺]/[PAMAM] and reaches a maximum demonstrating the strong complexation. After attaining the maximum, the intensity of the *d-d* transition band decreases with bathochromic shift suggesting its gradual distortion in the complexation geometry.

Cyclic voltammetric study of the dendron-Cu^{II} com-

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra for titration of 1 with CuCl₂.

Fig. 2. Titration curve for 1 with CuCl₂.

plex was performed in water solution using KCl as the supporting electrolyte in the potential range 2 V to -0.75 V. The cyclic voltammogram for this complex is shown in Fig. 3. The complex shows two re-oxidation waves at relatively more positive potentials than that of aqueous solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O evidencing the complex formation of PAMAM dendron with Cu^{II}. The quasi-irreversibility nature of the voltammetric response of dendron-Cu^{II} complex is most likely due to the insulating effect of the PAMAM dendron, which hinders the electron transfer process between the PAMAM-Cu^{II} complex and the electrode surface.

Thus the complexation of the polytopic dendritic ligand (PAMAM) 1 with Cu^{II} ion was investigated by UV-Vis spectroscopy and cyclic voltammetric study. Such metal ion complexing ability of PAMAM dendritic structure should be a strong excitement to workers in the fields of

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of (a) CuCl₂, aq. solution ($6 \times 10^{-2} M$); (b) Cu^{II}-dendron complex ($[Cu^{2+}]/[1] = 4 : 1$), V vs Ag/AgCl, scan rate = 0.2 V/s, room temperature.

polymer chemistry, biology and materials science. Further study is under progress.

Experimental

PAMAM dendron **1** was synthesized as described in our previously reported⁷ procedure. The complexation behaviour of PAMAM dendron towards Cu^{II} ion was examined by Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Upon successive addition of Cu^{II} ions to the methanolic solution of PAMAM dendron **1**, a gradual increase in absorbance at 650 nm belonging to the copper *d-d* transition was observed, reflecting the formation of the complex. Stoichiometry for the complex formed with PAMAM dendron was then investigated. Cyclic voltammetric (CV) study of the dendron-Cu^{II} complex was performed in water solution using glassy carbon as working and saturated Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode. KCl was used as the supporting electrolyte (0.1 M).

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